

Case Study

Fraud Prevention in Bumdes Fund Management with Internal Locus of Control as a Moderating Variable

Risdan Arianto¹

Department of Accounting, University of Mataram, Mataram, Indonesia

Akram Akram

Department of Accounting, University of Mataram, Mataram, Indonesia

Taufiq Chaidir

Department of Accounting, University of Mataram, Mataram, Indonesia

Received 25 January 2025 Revised 6 March 2025 Accepted 9 March 2025

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of individual morality and internal control systems on fraud prevention, with internal locus of control as a moderating variable, in Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) in Sumbawa Regency. The study population includes BUMDes leaders and treasurers throughout Sumbawa Regency. The sampling technique used a purposive sampling method with a sample size of 76 BUMDes and 152 respondents, consisting of BUMDes leaders and treasurers. The results of the study indicate that partially, individual morality and internal control systems have a positive and significant effect on fraud prevention. In addition, internal locus of control moderates the influence of individual morality on fraud prevention positively. However, internal locus of control negatively moderates the influence of internal control systems on fraud prevention. The implications of this study provide insight to stakeholders in improving individual morality and the effectiveness of internal control systems to minimize the risk of fraud in BUMDes.

Keywords: Individual morality, internal control system, internal locus of control, fraud prevention.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: risdanarianto63@gmail.com

Introduction

Rural development has a very strategic role in the context of national development, considering that rural areas cover most of Indonesia's territory. Data shows that around 70% of Indonesia's total population still lives in rural areas (Widiyaningsih & Yani, 2023). The success of national development cannot be separated from how development in villages is managed and improved. In this case, the village government together with the local community has the responsibility to explore, manage, and utilize the available natural resources to improve the welfare of its people.

Development in rural areas should not only focus on infrastructure aspects, but should also include strengthening human resources. Rural communities need to have access to education, training, and various empowerment programs so that they can improve their skills and capacities in various fields. Thus, the creativity and productivity of rural communities will continue to grow, and their awareness of the environment will also increase. This will have an impact on improving the quality of life of rural communities in a sustainable manner.

As an effort to accelerate development in villages, the central government launched the Village Fund program in 2015. Since it was first introduced, this program has become a strategic policy aimed at accelerating development and community empowerment at the village level. The Village Fund functions as a stimulus for villages in carrying out various development programs, both physical ones such as building roads, bridges, and irrigation, as well as non-physical ones such as empowering the community's economy, skills training, and improving the quality of health and education services.

Over time, the allocation of Village Funds disbursed by the central government continues to increase from year to year. The government is committed to continuing to distribute Village Funds so that they can be optimally utilized by village governments to improve the economic conditions of the community, narrow the gap between villages and cities, and improve social welfare. The following are details regarding the amount of Village Funds that have been disbursed by the central government to local governments over the past few years in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Fund Development Graph
Source: Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration of the Republic of Indonesia

Regulation of the Minister of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration of the Republic of Indonesia Number 13 of 2023 places special emphasis on various crucial aspects in the utilization of Village Funds. In the regulation, there are several priority areas that must be considered in the use of Village Funds, including efforts to address extreme poverty, strengthen food and animal security, accelerate the reduction in stunting rates, and develop strategic sectors in villages through the provision of capital assistance for Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) and Joint BUMDes. The government's support for these aspects reflects a strong commitment to encouraging locally-based economic growth by paying special attention to initiatives that are oriented towards improving the welfare of village communities (Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, 2023)

In practice, efforts to improve the economic base in rural areas have long been part of the development policies implemented by village governments. Various programs have been implemented to empower rural communities and optimize local potential in order to create sustainable sources of income. However, the realization of these initiatives has not yet fully achieved satisfactory results as expected. The government continues to develop new approaches that are more effective and oriented towards direct community economic empowerment. One strategy that is considered to have great potential in driving and accelerating the village economy is encouraging entrepreneurial activities through the management of Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes).

BUMDes is an economic instrument designed to be a catalyst in the development of locally-based businesses. The existence of BUMDes allows villages to manage their own resources independently in order to create added value for the local community. In addition, BUMDes can also act as a liaison between village communities and wider markets, both at the regional and national levels. Through this approach, it is hoped that village communities will not only become consumers in economic activities, but also become the main actors who contribute to the economic growth of their own villages.

Based on data released by the Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration of the Republic of Indonesia, the number of Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) that have been formed nationally reached 59,635 units in 2023 (Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, 2023). This figure shows a significant increase compared to previous years, reflecting the high enthusiasm of village governments and communities in utilizing local potential to improve their standard of living.

The existence of Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) is a hope for many elements of society and stakeholders in an effort to create more equitable prosperity in rural areas. BUMDes is expected to be the main driving force in developing potential economic sectors in villages, such as agriculture, fisheries, livestock, creative industries, and the service and trade sectors. In addition, the success of BUMDes in managing village-based businesses will also contribute to increasing Village Original Income (PADes), which can ultimately be reused to finance various other development programs.

Economic empowerment based on BUMDes is also expected to create more job opportunities for rural communities, thereby reducing unemployment and preventing

uncontrolled urbanization. With wider job opportunities in the village, the young generation of the village no longer needs to look for work in the city, but can build their own careers and businesses in their hometowns. Thus, BUMDes is not only a business institution, but also a strategic instrument in encouraging village economic independence and strengthening the competitiveness of rural communities amidst increasingly competitive economic dynamics.

Government efforts to maximize the management of Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) are indeed very important to encourage village economic independence and improve the welfare of local communities. However, on the other hand, optimizing BUMDes can also give rise to various new challenges, one of which is the risk of fraud in fund management. Cases of misuse of BUMDes funds for personal gain still often occur, both by certain individuals and by groups that have access to BUMDes financial management.

Fraud in village financial management is a deliberate act to manipulate data or financial reports in order to gain personal or group benefits. This action can have a negative impact on village finances and cause losses to interested entities, including the village community itself. In many cases, this fraud involves the practice of embezzlement, falsification of financial reports, budget manipulation, and various other forms of abuse of authority.

This phenomenon not only occurs in the management of BUMDes but also reflects broader challenges in financial governance at the village and local government levels. Transparency International, through its Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) report, shows that Indonesia still faces serious problems in efforts to eradicate corruption. In 2023, Indonesia scored 34 out of 100 and was ranked 115 out of 180 countries surveyed. This score is relatively low and shows that corruption is still a significant problem in various sectors, including in the management of village funds and BUMDes (Corruption Perceptions Index, 2023).

The low CPI score also reflects the weak monitoring system for the use of public funds and the low level of transparency in financial management in various government agencies. This condition causes the level of public trust in the government to decrease, so that their participation in various village development programs also decreases. In addition, the lack of transparency can also reduce the level of compliance with established regulations, because the community feels that existing policies are not implemented fairly and tend to benefit certain parties.

This research focuses on Sumbawa Regency, West Nusa Tenggara Province. Sumbawa Regency was chosen as the research location due to its significant number of Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes). The total number of BUMDes in Sumbawa Regency reaches 157 units spread across 24 districts. In reality, many BUMDes managers in Sumbawa Regency still lack an understanding of the essence of BUMDes itself. Most existing BUMDes in Sumbawa Regency are primarily focused on savings and loan businesses (Hikmah, 2020). However, referring to Law No. 6 of 2014 on Villages, which serves as the foundation for the establishment of BUMDes, villages are encouraged to have a business entity that aims to meet the community's needs, particularly basic

necessities. Additionally, there should be competent human resources capable of managing the business entity as a driving force for the local economy. As a result, many villages fail to implement their programs in accordance with regulatory mandates. This situation makes them vulnerable to fund misappropriation. Several instances of fraud in Sumbawa Regency, West Nusa Tenggara Province, are as follows.

Table 1 Fraud Phenomenon in Sumbawa Regency, West Nusa Tenggara Province

No	Phenomenon	Loss Amount (Rp)	Date	Data source	Downloaded date
1	Sumbawa District Attorney Investigates Alleged Corruption of Tepal Village-Owned Enterprise Funds of Rp 700 Million	700 million	November 14, 2023	https://regional.kompas.com/read/2023/11/14/153945878/kejari-sumbawa-usut-dugaan-korupsi-dana-bumdes-tepal-rp-700-juta	September 22, 2024

Based on Table 1, it is evident that corruption in BUMDes funds has occurred in Sumbawa Regency. As previously known, the former Head of Tepal Village, Batulanteh District, Sumbawa Regency, Ali Amrullah, was reported to the Sumbawa District Attorney's Office regarding alleged corruption involving the budget of BUMDes "Alang," amounting to approximately IDR 700 million.

Hundreds of millions of rupiahs had been allocated to the community. However, after further inspection, numerous irregularities were discovered in the distribution of these funds. The financial records indicated a loan of IDR 5 million, but in reality, the community only received IDR 2 million. Additionally, there was a purchase of musical instruments by BUMDes worth IDR 75 million, even though the purchase had already been budgeted through the Village Budget (APBDes) for IDR 50 million.

One of the main factors causing widespread fraud in BUMDes management is the lack of a strict accountability system and weak internal monitoring system. Many villages do not yet have adequate audit mechanisms to ensure that the use of BUMDes funds is carried out transparently and in accordance with its original purpose. In addition, the low level of public understanding of their rights to monitor the use of village funds also contributes to the increasing risk of misuse of funds.

To overcome this problem, concrete steps are needed that can increase transparency and accountability in the management of BUMDes. The government needs to strengthen the monitoring mechanism by implementing a periodic audit system carried out by an independent institution. In addition, digitalization of the village financial system can also be a solution to reduce the opportunity for data manipulation and increase openness in fund management.

The active role of the community is very important in overseeing the use of BUMDes funds. Village communities need to be encouraged to be more proactive in supervising and reporting if they find indications of misuse of funds. Education and socialization regarding the rights and obligations of the community in managing village funds must continue to be improved. With stricter supervision and more active community participation, it is hoped that the potential for fraud in BUMDes management can be minimized, so that the funds allocated can truly be used for the benefit of development and the welfare of the village community (Azizah, 2020) .

Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) in Sumbawa Regency have a strategic role in supporting the improvement of village community welfare through the utilization of local resources and village-based economic development. However, in practice, the existence of BUMDes in the region still faces various challenges that hinder the achievement of its ideal goals. Although it is expected to be a driving force for a transparent and accountable village economy, the reality on the ground shows that there are still various obstacles that need to be overcome immediately so that BUMDes can function optimally.

Obstacles in BUMDes management can be categorized into internal and external factors. From the internal side, the morality and ethics of BUMDes administrators are one of the factors that influence the success of village business management. Indecisiveness in implementing the principles of transparency and accountability often leads to unprofessional management. In addition, the opportunity to commit deviations due to weak supervision systems, individual economic pressures, and demands for personal needs can encourage administrators to misuse BUMDes funds for personal gain. In certain situations, the lack of strict supervision causes some administrators to feel that they have full authority over the funds managed, resulting in practices that are not in accordance with the principles of good governance.

From the external side, weak supervision from external parties and low community involvement in supervising BUMDes management also contributed to the worsening condition. The minimal community participation in the management and supervision process gave the management more room to act without adequate control. In fact, as a village-owned business, active community involvement in every stage of management is a key factor in ensuring transparency and accountability. The ambiguity in financial reporting and the emergence of various irregularities also resulted in a decrease in the level of public trust in BUMDes management. The community began to doubt the integrity of the management, resulting in a negative perception of the role of BUMDes which should be the driver of the village economy.

To overcome this problem, there needs to be a comprehensive improvement effort that covers internal and external aspects. From the internal side, it is important to strengthen the morality and ethics of BUMDes administrators through capacity building, anti-corruption education, and the implementation of a stricter governance system in financial management. The implementation of an effective internal control system can help reduce the risk of irregularities and ensure that BUMDes funds are used in accordance with the intended purpose.

From the external side, tighter supervision from local governments and communities must be strengthened to ensure transparency and accountability in the management of BUMDes. Village communities as the legitimate owners of BUMDes need to be more empowered to have an active role in overseeing the running of village businesses. Socialization regarding the rights and obligations of the community in the management of BUMDes must also be increased, so that the community can better understand the importance of their involvement in ensuring the success of this village business.

With the improvement efforts in the governance system, transparency, and increasing community participation, it is hoped that BUMDes in Sumbawa Regency can truly function as the main driver in improving the welfare of village communities. The public trust that had declined must be rebuilt through real commitment from all parties involved in the management of BUMDes. If better governance can be implemented consistently, then BUMDes will be able to become an effective instrument in encouraging sustainable village economic growth.

The results of this study indicate that individual morality has a significant and positive influence on fraud prevention efforts. This finding is in line with a study conducted by (Alvaro & Octavia, 2019) which states that the higher a person's level of morality, the greater their ability to prevent fraud. Individuals with high morality tend to avoid behavior that can harm society, organizations, or the state. Village officials who have strong moral integrity will certainly be more responsible in carrying out the mandate given by the government. The results of this study contradict the study conducted by (Azizah, 2020) which concluded that individual morality does not have a significant influence on fraud prevention in village fund management.

Furthermore, this study shows that the internal control system has a positive and significant effect on fraud prevention. This finding is consistent with the study by (Wardana, 2017), which states that the higher the internal control system, the higher the level of fraud prevention.

The uniqueness of this study compared to previous research lies in the use of a moderating variable, namely internal locus of control. This variable plays a role in strengthening the relationship between individual morality and the internal control system in fraud prevention. Individuals with a high internal locus of control tend to be more responsible for their actions and better able to regulate themselves in situations that may trigger fraud. Internal locus of control can be defined as the extent to which individuals believe that the outcomes of their actions are the result of their own efforts (Adnyani & Dantes, 2022)

Research Model

Figure 2. Research Model

Hypothesis

Individual Morality Influences Fraud Prevention Efforts

Rahimah & Lysandra, (2018) stated that individuals who uphold morality can avoid fraud because those who prioritize moral values tend to adhere to applicable norms in accordance with ethical principles. In contrast, individuals who do not uphold morality make decisions based on their own desires while neglecting obligations and regulations that should be followed.

The study by Alvaro & Octavia (2019) found that individual morality has a positive and significant effect on fraud prevention in village fund management. The higher the individual's morality, the greater the prevention of fraud in village fund management. However, these findings contradict the research conducted by (Azizah, 2020) which concluded that individual morality does not have a significant effect on fraud prevention in village fund management. Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H₁: Individual Morality Positively Influences Fraud Prevention Efforts in BUMDes Fund Management Across Sumbawa Regency.

Internal Control System Influences Fraud Prevention Efforts

Sujana & Ari, (2020) stated that the stronger the internal control system in village governance, the more effectively it can prevent or reduce fraud. Conversely, if internal control is weak, the likelihood of fraud increases. Similarly, Wardana, (2017) found that the internal control system has a positive and significant effect on fraud prevention. The

higher the level of internal control, the greater the fraud prevention efforts. Internal control is crucial as it aims to minimize the chances of errors and behaviors that deviate from established regulations (Armelia & Wahyuni, 2020). Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H₂: The Internal Control System Has a Positive Influence on Fraud Prevention Efforts in BUMDes Fund Management Across Sumbawa Regency.

Internal Locus of Control Moderates the Influence of Individual Morality on Fraud Prevention Efforts

Internal locus of control refers to the degree to which an individual views events in his or her life as a consequence of his or her actions, and thus as controllable by the individual himself or herself (Dewi & Rasmini, 2019). A person with an Internal Locus of Control tends to view everything they experience—whether events, occurrences, fate, or destiny—as being the result of their own control, allowing them to manage the situations and conditions they face.

Rotter as cited in Pinasti, (2016), stated that individuals with an Internal Locus of Control believe that the events they experience are the consequences of their own behavior and actions. They have good control over their self-assessments, are more likely to influence others, and believe that their efforts will lead to success. They are proactive in seeking information or knowledge about the situations they encounter.

This study argues that Internal Locus of Control will moderate the influence of individual morality on the tendency for accounting fraud. This is because individuals with an Internal Locus of Control believe that everything that happens to them is due to their own actions, making them more capable of controlling the desire to commit fraud. Based on theory, previous research, and the arguments presented above, the hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H₃: Internal locus of control moderates the influence of individual morality on efforts to prevent fraud in the management of Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) funds in Sumbawa Regency.

Internal Locus of Control Moderates the Influence of Internal Control on Fraud Prevention Efforts

An individual with an internal locus of control has a self-belief that they are capable of managing their problems correctly without resorting to fraud (Sari, 2021). Individuals with a high Internal Locus of Control strongly believe that they have full control over the outcomes of their actions and feel deeply responsible for adhering to and implementing internal control procedures. This belief leads them to view compliance with rules and internal control procedures as an integral part of their personal responsibility. As a result, internal control becomes more effective in reducing the tendency for fraud in individuals with a high internal locus of control, as they actively strive to ensure that their actions align not only with applicable policies but also with personal integrity and ethics. Based

on theory, previous research, and the arguments above, the researcher proposes the following hypothesis:

H4: Internal locus of control moderates the influence of the internal control system on efforts to prevent fraud in the management of Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) funds in Sumbawa Regency.

Material and Methods

This study uses an associative research method with a quantitative approach to analyze the impact of specific factors on fraud prevention in the management of Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes), with internal locus of control as a moderating variable. A quantitative approach was chosen as it allows for the objective measurement of relationships between variables through numerical data and statistical analysis. Data in this study were collected via surveys using questionnaires distributed to managers and treasurers of BUMDes in Sumbawa Regency, West Nusa Tenggara Province. The instruments were developed based on the indicators contained in the research variables, which were then elaborated in the questionnaire items.

The research was conducted in the Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) in Sumbawa Regency, with a total of 157 BUMDes. However, it is important to note that, at the time of the research, only 76 BUMDes were actively operating. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling, with the criteria that respondents must have a role in managing the finances of BUMDes.

Data analysis was carried out using moderation regression tests to examine the relationship between independent variables and fraud prevention, as well as to see the role of internal locus of control as a variable that strengthens or weakens that relationship. Validity and reliability tests were conducted to ensure the quality of the research instruments. With this method, the research aims to provide empirical understanding of the factors that can enhance the effectiveness of BUMDes fund management and prevent fraud practices, thereby serving as a basis for recommendations for managers and relevant stakeholders.

The analysis stage was carried out using the SmartPLS Version 4 software. The advantage of the PLS method is that the data does not need to follow a multivariate normal distribution, sample size does not need to be large, and PLS can be used not only to confirm theories but also to explain the presence or absence of relationships between latent variables.

Drawing Path Diagrams

Figure 3. Drawing Path Diagrams

The data analysis method used in this study is the SEM-PLS method with the Smart PLS version 4.0 program. The first step in the PLS-SEM analysis is model conceptualization. The measurement model in this study uses a reflective outer model. The individual morality variable (X1) is measured using six statement indicators, the internal control system variable (X2) is measured using ten statement indicators, the internal locus of control variable (Z) is measured using eight indicators, and fraud prevention (Y) is measured using eight statement indicators.

Questionnaire Distribution Data

Table 2. Questionnaire Distribution Data

Information	Amount
Distributed questionnaires	152
Returned questionnaire	128
Unreturned questionnaires	24
Questionnaire Return Rate	84,21%

Based on the table 2, it can be explained that the response rate of the questionnaires is 84.2%. A total of 152 questionnaires were distributed for this study to the leaders and treasurers of Village-Owned Enterprises in Sumbawa Regency. Out of the distributed questionnaires, 128 were returned, while 24 questionnaires were not returned, representing 12 Village-Owned Enterprises.

Outer Model

Descriptive Statistics

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
X1	128	1	5	3,646	0,963	-0,572	-0,120
X2	128	1	5	3,879	0,817	-0,555	0,182
Y	128	1	5	4,007	0,701	-0,875	1,554
Z	128	1	5	3,904	0,867	-1,176	1,548

The respondents' perception of individual morality (X1) at village-owned enterprises (bumdes) shows an average score of 3.646, indicating that the respondents tend to rate it as relatively good.

The assessment of the internal control system (X2) has an average score of 3.879, which is slightly higher than individual morality, reflecting a more positive view from the respondents.

Fraud prevention (Y) in bumdes received the highest average score of 4.007, indicating that respondents have a very positive view of the fraud prevention efforts.

The respondents' perception of internal locus of control (Z) at bumdes has an average score of 3.904, showing a fairly positive perspective.

Convergent Validity

Table 4. Convergent Validity

Variable	Indicator	Mark	Information
Individual Morality (X1)	X1.1	0.751	Valid
	X1.2	0.77	Valid
	X1.3	0.761	Valid
	X1.4	0.729	Valid
	X1.5	0.786	Valid
	X1.6	0.829	Valid
Internal Control System (X2)	X2.1	0.751	Valid
	X2.2	0.77	Valid
	X2.3	0.761	Valid
	X2.4	0.729	Valid
	X2.5	0.786	Valid
	X2.6	0.829	Valid
	X2.7	0.792	Valid
	X2.8	0.82	Valid
	X2.9	0.829	Valid

Variable	Indicator	Mark	Information
	X2.10	0.766	Valid
Prevention Fraud (Y)	Y.1	0.85	Valid
	Y.2	0.75	Valid
	Y.3	0.863	Valid
	Y.4	0.721	Valid
	Y.5	0.825	Valid
	Y.6	0.796	Valid
	Y.7	0.84	Valid
	Y.8	0.768	Valid
Internal Locus Of Control (Z)	Z.1	0.864	Valid
	Z.2	0.775	Valid
	Z.3	0.737	Valid
	Z.4	0.791	Valid
	Z.5	0.745	Valid
	Z.6	0.882	Valid
	Z.7	0.855	Valid
	Z.8	0.747	Valid

The results of the analysis in Table 4. indicate that the factor loading values for all indicators of each construct are greater than 0.7. this suggests that each indicator is capable of effectively measuring its respective variable in the study.

Discriminant Validity

Table 5. Discriminant Validity

	X1	X2	Y	Z	Z X X2	Z X X1
X1.1	0.762	0.387	0.584	0.478	-0.317	-0.382
X1.2	0.800	0.487	0.638	0.627	-0.293	-0.317
X1.3	0.867	0.485	0.634	0.517	-0.328	-0.376
X1.4	0.864	0.505	0.651	0.554	-0.272	-0.347
X1.5	0.868	0.461	0.582	0.600	-0.289	-0.372
X1.6	0.863	0.463	0.613	0.624	-0.300	-0.384
X2.1	0.516	0.751	0.651	0.670	-0.448	-0.492
X2.2	0.539	0.770	0.614	0.628	-0.336	-0.353
X2.3	0.487	0.761	0.642	0.468	-0.317	-0.286
X2.4	0.297	0.729	0.489	0.356	0.014	0.001
X2.5	0.442	0.786	0.473	0.484	-0.227	-0.216
X2.6	0.562	0.829	0.740	0.616	-0.364	-0.288
X2.7	0.400	0.792	0.564	0.458	-0.329	-0.326
X2.8	0.361	0.820	0.636	0.467	-0.368	-0.338
X2.9	0.357	0.829	0.483	0.385	-0.252	-0.214
X2.10	0.288	0.766	0.462	0.341	-0.223	-0.200

Y.1	0.676	0.599	0.850	0.625	-0.411	-0.374
Y.2	0.424	0.634	0.750	0.526	-0.216	-0.153
Y.3	0.624	0.610	0.863	0.628	-0.282	-0.222
Y.4	0.601	0.476	0.721	0.490	-0.432	-0.360
Y.5	0.633	0.640	0.825	0.637	-0.502	-0.391
Y.6	0.644	0.608	0.796	0.552	-0.286	-0.232
Y.7	0.612	0.660	0.840	0.715	-0.505	-0.464
Y.8	0.505	0.594	0.768	0.598	-0.316	-0.312
Z.1	0.612	0.450	0.589	0.864	-0.297	-0.347
Z.2	0.556	0.620	0.731	0.775	-0.558	-0.466
Z.3	0.441	0.598	0.602	0.737	-0.332	-0.340
Z.4	0.435	0.383	0.460	0.791	-0.195	-0.266
Z.5	0.522	0.366	0.449	0.745	-0.268	-0.335
Z.6	0.605	0.583	0.731	0.882	-0.399	-0.411
Z.7	0.632	0.486	0.629	0.855	-0.386	-0.420
Z.8	0.493	0.520	0.449	0.747	-0.400	-0.386
Z X X1	-0.432	-0.361	-0.394	-0.471	0.862	1.000
Z X X2	-0.358	-0.380	-0.463	-0.457	1.000	0.862

Based on the table 5, it shows that the loading of indicators to the measured construct is higher than the loading to other constructs. therefore, it can be concluded that all indicators meet the criteria for discriminant validity, meaning the indicators are valid.

Composite Reliability

Table 6. Composite Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Individual Morality (X1)	0,915	0,916
Internal Control System (X2)	0,930	0,936
Prevention Fraud (Y)	0,921	0,924
Internal Locos of Control (Z)	0,920	0,933

From the table 6, it can be observed that the calculation results for composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha for all constructs are greater than 0.70. This indicates that respondents were consistent in answering the questions. Therefore, it can be concluded that all constructs have a good level of reliability.

Discussion

F-Square

The following researchers present the f-square values for each variable:

Table 7. F-Square Results

Variables	F- Square
Individual Morality (X1)	0.319
Internal Control System (X2)	0.329
<i>Internal Locus Of Control (Z)</i>	0.112

Based on the data presented in Table 7, it is known that the individual morality variable (X1) and the internal control system (X2) have f-Square values of 0.319 and 0.329 respectively, indicating that both are in the moderate category. Meanwhile, the internal locus of control variable (Z) has an f-Square value of 0.112, which is relatively low. Thus, it can be concluded that individual morality (X1) and the internal control system (X2) provide a greater contribution to the dependent variable compared to the internal locus of control (Z), whose role is relatively small.

R- Square (R²)

Table 8. R-Squares Values

Variables	R- Square
<i>Fraud Prevention (Y)</i>	0.776

Based on the data presented in Table 8, it is known that the R-Squares value of the relationship between individual morality variables and internal control systems on fraud prevention with moderation from internal locus of control is 0.776 or 77.6%. This value is quite high, which means that the combination of individual morality variables and internal control systems is able to explain 77.6% of the variability in fraud prevention, with the additional role of internal locus of control as a moderating variable.

The remaining 22.4% is explained by other factors not included in this research model. These factors can be other aspects that influence fraud prevention, such as organizational culture, external pressure, legal regulations, surveillance technology, and the level of ethical awareness of individuals in the organization. In other words, although individual morality and internal control systems have a very strong role in preventing fraud, there are still other external factors that can also have an impact on the effectiveness of fraud prevention in an organization.

The results of this study indicate that the higher the level of individual morality and the stronger the implementation of the internal control system in an organization, the greater the possibility of fraud prevention. The existence of internal locus of control as a moderating variable also plays an important role in strengthening or weakening the relationship. Organizations need to not only emphasize improving individual morality

and internal control systems, but also consider the internal locus of control factors possessed by each individual in the organization so that fraud prevention strategies can be more optimal.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 9. Results of Path Coefficient Analysis

	Original sample	t statistics	P values	Conclusion
X1 → Y	0.382	5,969	0,000	Accepted
X2 → Y	0.365	5,496	0,000	Accepted
Z x X1 → Y	0.207	2,156	0.031	Accepted
Z x X2 → Y	-0.224	2,459	0.014	Rejected

Based on Table 9, the results of the analysis for testing the research hypothesis can be described with the following explanation:

1) First Hypothesis Testing (H₁)

The t-value for the influence of individual morality on fraud prevention is 5.969, greater than the t-table which is 1.96 with a path coefficient value of 0.382. The p-value for the influence of individual morality on fraud prevention is 0.000, smaller than the alpha value of 0.05. It can be concluded that the first hypothesis (H₁) which states that individual morality has a positive effect on fraud prevention is accepted.

2) Testing the Second Hypothesis (H₂)

The t-value for the influence of the internal control system on fraud prevention is 5.496 which is 1.96 with a path coefficient value of 0.365. The p-value for the influence of the internal control system on fraud prevention is 0.000, which is smaller than the alpha value of 0.05. It can be concluded that the second hypothesis (H₂) which states that the internal control system has a positive effect on fraud prevention is accepted.

3) Third Hypothesis Testing (H₃)

The t-value for The internal locus of control variable strengthens the influence between individual morality and fraud prevention is 2.156 greater than the t-table which is 1.96 with a path coefficient value of 0.207. The p value for the influence of internal locus of control strengthens the influence between individual morality and fraud prevention by 0.031, which is smaller than the alpha value of 0.05. It can be concluded that the third hypothesis (H₃) which states that internal locus of control strengthens the influence between individual morality and fraud prevention is accepted

4) Testing the Fourth Hypothesis (H₄)

The t-value for the internal locus of control variable strengthens the influence between the internal control system and fraud prevention is 2.459, which is 1.96 with a path coefficient value of -0.224. The p-value for the internal locus of control variable

strengthens the influence between the internal control system and fraud prevention by 0.014, which is smaller than the alpha value of 0.05. It can be concluded that the fourth hypothesis (H4) which states that the internal locus of control variable strengthens the influence between the internal control system and fraud prevention is rejected.

Moderation Effect Testing

Table 10. Moderation Effects

	P values	F- Square	Information	Conclusion
Z x X1 → Y	0.031	0.112 (high)	Significant	Quasi Moderation
Z x X2 → Y	0.014	0.138 (high)	Significant	Quasi Moderation

Based on Table 10, the results of the moderation effect can be described as follows:

1. The P- value of individual morality (X1) on *fraud prevention* (Y) after being moderated by *internal locus of control* (Z) has a value of 0.031 which means less than 0.05 so that it has a significant effect. So, *the internal locus of control* moderates the influence of individual morality on *fraud prevention*, including in the quasi-moderation category. Meanwhile, if you look at the f- square, it has a value of 0.112 which means above 0.025 so that the resulting moderation effect is included in the high category.

2. The P- value of the internal control system (X2) on *fraud prevention* (Y) after being moderated by *internal locus of control* (Z) has a value of 0.014 which means less than 0.05 so that it has a significant effect. So, *the internal locus of control* moderates the influence of the internal control system on *fraud prevention*, including in the quasi-moderation category. Meanwhile, if you look at the f- square, it has a value of 0.138 which means above 0.025 so that the resulting moderation effect is included in the high category.

The Influence of Individual Morality on Fraud Prevention

The first hypothesis (H1) in this study states that individual morality has a positive influence on fraud prevention. Based on the results of the analysis conducted, it was found that the individual morality variable has a significant effect on fraud prevention, with an original sample value of 0.382 and a p-value of 0.000. Given that the p-value is less than 0.05, the first hypothesis (H1) can be accepted. Thus, it can be concluded that the higher the level of individual morality, the greater the ability to prevent fraud in the management of BUMDes funds in Sumbawa Regency.

Individuals with high levels of morality tend to have a stronger ethical awareness, which makes them more compliant with norms, rules, and ethical principles in carrying out their duties. Conversely, individuals with low morality are more susceptible to taking actions that are contrary to applicable rules, including fraud in managing funds. Someone who upholds moral values will consider the ethical impact of each decision taken more, so they are more likely to avoid fraud. In the context of managing BUMDes funds, high morality among managers will minimize abuse of authority and increase transparency in financial management.

The results of this study are in line with previous findings conducted by Pamungkas, (2019) which stated that individual morality has a positive and significant influence on fraud prevention. This indicates that individuals who have a high level of morality will be more committed to carrying out their duties with integrity and responsibility. Individual morality is an internal factor that acts as an ethical foundation in forming behavior that is oriented towards honesty and compliance with applicable rules.

The results of this study also strengthen the understanding within the Agency Theory framework, which highlights the importance of control mechanisms and ethical aspects in reducing conflicts of interest between principals (community) and agents (BUMDes managers). In this context, agents (BUMDes managers) have an obligation to act in accordance with the interests of the principal (community). However, in practice, agents have the opportunity to act opportunistically by prioritizing their personal interests over the interests of the principal. With high individual morality, agents will be more likely to maintain their integrity and avoid actions that can harm the principal.

The findings of this study also confirm that individual morality not only plays a role in the context of regulatory compliance, but is also a major factor in building a more integrity-based organizational culture. In a work environment filled with individuals with high morality, the risk of fraud will be reduced due to the collective awareness to maintain transparency and accountability in financial management.

The Influence of Internal Control Systems on Fraud Prevention

The second hypothesis (H2) in this study states that the internal control system has a positive influence on fraud prevention. Based on the results of the analysis that has been carried out, it was found that the internal control system variable significantly affects fraud prevention, with an original sample value of 0.365 and a p-value of 0.000. Given that the p-value is less than 0.05, the second hypothesis (H2) is accepted. Thus, these results indicate that the better the internal control system implemented in an organization, the higher the effectiveness in preventing fraud in the management of BUMDes funds in Sumbawa Regency.

The internal control system is a mechanism designed to ensure that the organization's operational processes run effectively, efficiently, and in accordance with applicable regulations. This system includes various procedures and policies that aim to increase transparency, accountability, and supervision in financial management. One of the main functions of the internal control system is to minimize the risk of fraud through various strict controls and evaluation mechanisms. With a strong internal control system, every transaction and financial decision can be better monitored, so that the opportunity for fraud becomes smaller (Rani & Azlan, 2021).

The results of this study are consistent with the findings of (Hale et al., 2021) They emphasized that an effective internal control system can protect organizational assets, improve the reliability of financial reports, and ensure compliance with applicable policies and regulations. With strict supervision and clear control mechanisms, acts of misuse of funds or manipulation of financial reports can be minimized.

The results of this study also support the Agency Theory, which highlights the relationship between the principal (community) and the agent (BUMDes fund manager). In this theory, the fund manager acts as an agent who has the responsibility to manage financial resources as well as possible for the benefit of the community as the principal. However, in practice, there is a potential conflict of interest, where agents can act opportunistically and prioritize personal interests over the interests of the community. A strong oversight mechanism is needed to ensure that agents continue to carry out their duties with integrity and in accordance with organizational goals. The internal control system functions as the main instrument in reducing the risk of such conflicts of interest by ensuring transparency, accountability, and compliance with applicable regulations.

In addition to the supervisory aspect, the internal control system also plays a role in creating an organizational culture that is more oriented towards ethics and compliance. In an environment that has a good internal control system, each individual will be more motivated to carry out their duties responsibly and avoid actions that can harm the organization. This is important in the context of managing BUMDes funds, where the funds managed come from the community and must be used for the common good.

Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that strengthening the internal control system is very necessary in efforts to prevent fraud, especially in the management of BUMDes funds in Sumbawa Regency. Several strategic steps that can be implemented include improving internal audit mechanisms, developing a more transparent reporting system, and imposing strict sanctions on perpetrators of fraud. There needs to be an increase in capacity for fund managers through training and education related to the importance of the internal control system and its impact on organizational sustainability.

Internal Locus of Control Moderates the Influence of Individual Morality on Fraud Prevention

The third hypothesis (H3) in this study states that internal locus of control acts as a moderating variable that influences the relationship between internal control systems and fraud prevention. The results of the hypothesis test show that internal locus of control is proven to have an influence in moderating the relationship between individual morality and fraud prevention, with an original sample value of 0.207 and a p-value of 0.031. Because the p-value is smaller than 0.05, the third hypothesis (H3) in this study can be accepted. This finding indicates that internal locus of control has a significant influence on individual morality in fraud prevention efforts in a positive direction.

The positive direction of the influence of internal locus of control on the relationship between individual morality and fraud prevention in managing BUMDes funds throughout Sumbawa Regency shows that the higher the level of internal locus of control possessed by an individual, the greater the influence of individual morality in preventing fraud. Individuals with a high level of internal locus of control tend to have a greater awareness of ethics and responsibility in carrying out their duties. They believe that the actions taken will have a direct impact on the results obtained, both for themselves and for the organization and the surrounding community. This belief encourages individuals to be more careful in making decisions and avoiding actions that can pose risks, including fraud. (Hilman & Asmoro, 2020).

Based on the results of the moderation analysis, it was found that the moderating effect of internal locus of control on the relationship between individual morality and fraud prevention was categorized as quasi moderation. This means that internal locus of control not only acts as a moderating variable that influences the relationship, but also has a direct influence on fraud prevention. In other words, individuals who have a high level of morality but have a low internal locus of control may not be fully effective in preventing fraud. Strengthening the internal locus of control in individuals is a very important strategy in increasing the effectiveness of fraud prevention in the management of BUMDes funds throughout Sumbawa Regency.

The implication of the results of this study is the importance of organizations in paying attention to the internal locus of control aspect in the process of fund management and decision making. Organizations need to encourage individuals to have a high internal locus of control by providing training and education on the importance of individual responsibility in preventing fraud. The formation of an organizational culture that instills the values of integrity, transparency, and accountability can also help improve individuals' internal locus of control so that they are more aware of the importance of maintaining morality at work.

Organizations can also develop additional strategies to improve internal locus of control, such as giving individuals more authority in making decisions, ensuring an incentive system based on performance and integrity, and strengthening whistleblowing mechanisms so that individuals are more willing to report indications of fraud. By strengthening the internal locus of control, individuals will not only act in accordance with the rules set by the internal control system, but also actively engage in preventing fraud based on their personal awareness and moral values.

Internal Locus of Control Moderates the Influence of Internal Control Systems on Fraud Prevention

The fourth hypothesis (H4) in this study states that internal locus of control plays a role in moderating the relationship between internal control systems and fraud prevention. However, the results of hypothesis testing indicate that internal locus of control has a negative influence in moderating the relationship between internal control systems and fraud prevention, with an original sample value of -0.224 and a p-value of 0.014. Because the p-value is less than 0.05, the fourth hypothesis (H4) in this study is rejected. Although the results of the analysis indicate that internal locus of control does play a role in moderating the relationship, the direction of its influence is actually negative, which means that the existence of internal locus of control actually weakens the effectiveness of the internal control system in preventing fraud, especially in the context of managing BUMDes funds throughout Sumbawa Regency.

This finding is quite interesting because it contradicts the assumption that individuals with a high internal locus of control should have greater moral awareness and be more responsible in carrying out their duties. However, the results of this study indicate that in some situations, individuals with a high level of internal locus of control may actually have a tendency to ignore internal control systems. This is likely due to their belief that the decisions they make are completely under their personal control and that they do not

really need external control mechanisms such as internal control procedures that have been established by the organization.

In the context of BUMDes fund management, individuals with a high level of internal locus of control may feel that they can control the situation independently without having to follow the internal control system strictly. They may believe that decisions made based on personal experience and intuition are more effective than established standard procedures. As a result, they tend to under-appreciate the importance of monitoring and control mechanisms in preventing fraud.

Individuals who have high self-confidence in control over the results obtained can also show a level of skepticism towards procedures that are structural and bureaucratic. They may perceive the internal control system as too rigid, inflexible, or even inhibiting work efficiency. This attitude has the potential to cause them to ignore or not fully implement internal control procedures, which can ultimately increase the risk of fraud in the organization.

This finding is also in line with several previous studies showing that in some conditions, individuals with a high internal locus of control can experience overconfidence bias or excessive self-confidence in making decisions. Hilman & Asmoro (2020), for example, revealed that individuals with a very high internal locus of control often feel that they have more ability than others in managing risks and making the right decisions. As a result, they can tend to ignore the internal control system because they feel that they already have a strong enough personal mechanism to prevent errors and fraud.

Based on the results of moderation obtained in this study, it can be concluded that internal locus of control has a negative impact on the relationship between internal control systems and fraud prevention. In other words, individuals who have a high level of internal locus of control may find it more difficult to accept and implement internal control systems optimally. This is because they feel that the control carried out by the organizational system is not the main factor in preventing fraud, but rather that the individual's own decisions are more decisive in determining success in preventing fraud.

The implications of the results of this study are quite important for organizations that want to improve the effectiveness of internal control systems in preventing fraud. Organizations not only need to ensure that internal control systems are running well, but also need to understand how the characteristics of individuals who have a high internal locus of control can affect the effectiveness of the system.

Closing

Individual morality has a positive and significant influence on fraud prevention, meaning that the higher a person's morality, the greater their contribution to preventing fraudulent acts. Individual morality acts as an ethical basis for decision-making, especially in situations that have the potential to cause deviations. Values such as integrity, honesty, and responsibility are the main factors that encourage individuals to behave ethically and uphold transparency in managing funds. The internal control system

has also been shown to have a positive and significant influence on fraud prevention. This system functions as a monitoring mechanism that ensures that all organizational activities are carried out in accordance with applicable regulations, thereby minimizing the risk of abuse of authority.

The role of internal locus of control in moderating this relationship shows two different effects. Internal locus of control strengthens the influence of individual morality on fraud prevention, because individuals who have high internal control tend to be more responsible and uphold moral values in every decision they make. However, in the context of an internal control system, internal locus of control actually weakens its influence on fraud prevention. This shows that individuals with high internal control rely more on their personal decisions than following established procedures, potentially reducing the effectiveness of internal control in preventing fraud.

Research Limitations

This study has several limitations that can be improved in future research:

1. This study uses two exogenous variables, namely individual morality and internal control systems, as well as one moderating variable, internal locus of control, which influences fraud prevention as the endogenous variable. Based on data analysis using Smart PLS version 4.0, the R-Square value of 0.776 indicates that the model explains 77.6% of the variation in fraud prevention. However, this also suggests that 22.4% of the variation in fraud prevention is influenced by other variables not included in this research model.

2. The geographical factors of Sumbawa Regency, where the relatively long distances between villages pose challenges in distributing questionnaires. This condition caused delays in the data collection process in terms of both time and efficiency. Additionally, accessibility issues in some villages with limited transportation infrastructure further slowed down response rates from respondents.

3. This study is limited to the management of Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) funds in Sumbawa Regency, meaning that its findings and results are only applicable to this specific context. While the study provides valuable insights into the influence of individual morality, internal control systems, and internal locus of control on fraud prevention, these findings may not be fully generalizable to other financial management contexts, such as government organizations, private companies, or non-profit institutions.

4. Internal locus of control, as a moderating variable in this study, is psychological and subjective, leading to varying interpretations of responses. Although a standardized instrument was used, differences in respondents' perceptions could affect the validity of the research findings.

References

- Adnyani, N. K. S., & Dantes, N. (2022). Empowering customary villages in tourism development to realize inclusive economic growth of the Krama community. *Widya Laksana Journal*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.23887/jwl.v11i1.33827>

- Alvaro, R., & Octavia, E. (2019). Digital village: Potential and challenges increasing MSME credit through macroprudential intermediation ratio challenges of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 in the agricultural sector. *DPR Bulletin*, 4(8).
- Anak Agung K. Setiawan, A., Sujana, I. W., & Ari, N. N. (2020). The influence of self-efficacy and motivation on employee performance at PT Adi Sarana Armada Tbk Badung. *VALUES*, 1(2).
- Armelia, P. A., & Wahyuni, M. A. (2020). The influence of village apparatus competence, internal control effectiveness, and moral sensitivity on fraud prevention in village financial management. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 9, 61–70.
- Azizah, I. S. (2020). Participatory development of village communities: Study of the implementation of the village fund allocation program in Kledung District. *Journal of Maritime and Education (JME)*, 1.
- Dewi, N. K. P. P., & Rasmini, N. K. (2019). The influence of HR competence and locus of control on fraud prevention in village fund management. **Accounting E-Journal*, 29*(3), 9. <https://doi.org/10.24843/eja.2019.v29.i03.p12>
- Hale, C. B., Wadu, L. B., & Gultom, A. F. (2021). Citizen involvement in sustainable development to create a clean environment. *De Cive: Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan Pancasila dan Kewarganegaraan*, 1(12). <https://doi.org/10.56393/decive.v1i12.211>
- Hikmah, S. (2020). The role of village-owned enterprises (Bumdes) in increasing community income: A case study in Sabedo Village, Utan District, Sumbawa Regency [Unpublished undergraduate thesis]. State Islamic University of Mataram.
- Hilman, Y. A., & Asmoro, Y. R. (2020). The role of village government in implementing infrastructure development practices. *Jurnal Administrasi Pemerintahan Desa*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.47134/villages.v1i2.10>
- Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration of the Republic of Indonesia. (2023). Regulation of the Minister of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration Number 13 of 2023 on village fund utilization. <https://www.peraturan.go.id>
- Pamungkas, B. (2019). Implementation of village autonomy after Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning villages. *USM Law Review Journal*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.26623/julr.v2i2.2271>
- Pinasti, W. (2016). The influence of self-efficacy, locus of control, and demographic factors on career maturity of UIN Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta students [Unpublished undergraduate thesis]. Syarif Hidayatullah State Islamic University Jakarta.

- Rahimah, L. N., Murni, Y., & Lysandra, S. (2018). The influence of the presentation of village financial reports, control environment, and individual morality on preventing fraud in village fund allocations. *Scientific Journal of Economics*, 6(12), 139–154.
- Rani, H. A., & Azlan, M. (2021). Impact of Banda Aceh-Sigli toll road development on the environment. *Tameh: Journal of Civil Engineering*, 9(1).
<https://doi.org/10.37598/tameh.v9i1.100>
- Sari, N. (2021). The influence of financial literacy, locus of control, lifestyle, and gender on financial management behavior of students of State University of Surabaya. *Journal of Management Science*, 9(2), 672.
- Transparency International. (2023). Corruption Perceptions Index 2023.
<https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2023>
- Wardana, A. K. (2017). The influence of internal control, whistleblowing system, and officer morality on fraud prevention at the Public Works Department of Buleleng Regency [Unpublished undergraduate thesis]. Ganesha University of Education.
- Widiyaningsih, A. E., & Yani, M. T. (2023). Community participation in realizing a village aware of interfaith harmony in Laban Village, Menganti District, Gresik Regency. *Journal of Civics and Moral Studies*, 7(1), 44–60.
<https://doi.org/10.26740/jcms.v7n1.p44-60>

<p>COPYRIGHTS</p> <p>©2025 The Author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, as long as the original authors and source are cited. No permission is required from the authors or the publishers.</p>	
<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Arianto, R., Akram, A. and Chaidir, T. (2025). Fraud Prevention in Bumdes Fund Management with Internal Locus of Control as a Moderating Variable. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 12(4), 624-647.</p> <p>DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15492441</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_216941.html</p>	